

DESIGN METHODOLOGY FOR CFC STIFFENERS UNDER COMPRESSION AND FUEL PRESSURE LOADS

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ABSTRACT

Main critical loads for stiffeners are compression and internal fuel pressure loads. Leaving aside the buckling of stiffeners, the compression load leads to crippling failure while fuel pressure leads to skin-stiffener debonding. Both types of failure modes are quite different from those on metallic structures due to the absence of plasticity behaviour, the presence of delaminations initiated during manufacturing, produced by impacts or by an increase of interlaminar stresses, and the lack of data bases of material properties.

After a detailed analytical analysis, taking into account production requirements, a design methodology for stiffener shape selection has been established. Following that, semiempirical equations for crippling strain have been obtained, using results of a test series of 29 stiffeners, of 6 different configurations. Optimisation of test specimens was made with finite element models. For fuel pressure load, interlaminar stresses at skin-stiffener interface are obtained from detailed finite element models.

INTRODUCTION

Due to their excellent specific properties of modulus and strength, Composite Materials are widely used in aeronautical industry. Typical structure configuration of skin panels for a torque box is a thin skin with longitudinal and transversal stiffeners. Main critical loads for longitudinal stiffeners are compression load, combined or not with internal fuel pressure.

For high compression loaded elements the stiffener web may suffer a local buckling while the flange-web corner remains stable. A further increase in loads is supported by these corners until failure of the whole stiffener section or crippling of the stiffener. For metallic stiffener crippling failure is initiated by yield at the corners, and procedures to obtain crippling allowables are well known. For composite materials there are some differences, mainly delamination and brittle failures without plastic deformation.

There are some analytical procedures to obtain crippling strain for composite stiffeners[1], with a combination of analytical and semiempirical formulation.

The first goal of this report is to perform an analytical analysis in order to obtain a methodology to select stiffener shape taking into account structural and production requirements. A series of stiffener sections are selected for test. Test dimensions are optimized using finite element models. Correlation of test results with formulation of reference 1 will provide the final procedure for crippling strain allowables[6].

The second main load is internal fuel pressure. This load leads to skin-stiffener debonding. A finite element model is used to obtain the interlaminar stress distribution.

PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS OF STIFFENER SECTION

Stiffener can be divided in two groups according to the section shape. The first one is for closed section, like "hat" and "bead" section. The second group is for those with open section like T, I or J section.

Structural properties of "hat" and "bead" stiffeners are very similar. Closed section shows better properties for shear load than open section, also with thin laminates. Some problems of this type are the difficulty to manufacture and tie-in at frame or rib. Nowadays these stiffeners are not used for primary structures in wing/stabilizers torque box.

For open section stiffener only those with one axis of symmetry are selected in order to avoid the interaction of torsion failure with other types.

Structural requirements for stiffener selection are:

- No coupling between in plane and out of plane deformations, and tension and shear deformations. Stiffener laminate shall be symmetric and balanced.
- Axial stiffness, EA, obtained from general requirements of structure.
- Bending stiffness, EI, to increase buckling load between ribs. If adequate bending stiffness is provided there will be local buckling instead of global buckling.
- Crippling deformation far above from stiffened panel buckling values.

From the point of view of production it is desirable to build the stiffener section from one or two flat laminates, which can be folded in L or C shapes, and finally obtain the final stiffener section. Production of I type is more complex than T type due to the stiffener cap.

The analysis in this paper is done with T and I sections only. Consistent with manufacturing requirements, the same stacking sequence will be used for both types. Therefore the Young modulus of stiffener is a constant in the analysis.

The skin-stiffener assembly is divided into plates representing flanges, feet, wet, etc. For each

of those plates, crippling strain is obtained in reference 1 from empirical equation of the form:

$$\frac{\epsilon_{cr}}{\epsilon_{pl}} = \alpha \left(\frac{\epsilon_{cu}}{\epsilon_{pl}} \right)^\beta \quad (1)$$

where α y β depend of material and edge boundary conditions of the plate element; ϵ_{pl} is the local buckling strain of the plate element and ϵ_{cu} is the compression ultimate strain of plate element. Theoretical local buckling strain is obtained as a function of plate dimensions and laminate properties, in plane and flexural stiffness matrices:

- plates connected on both sides:

$$\epsilon_{pl} = \frac{2\pi^2}{b^2 t E_c} (\sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}} + D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \quad (2)$$

- plates connected on one side and free on the other:

$$\epsilon_{pl} = \frac{12D_{66}}{b^2 t E_c} + \frac{4\pi^2 D_{11}}{L^2 t E_c} \quad (3)$$

At this stage of stiffener selection ultimate strain of laminate is unknown so buckling strain is used instead of crippling strain. An initial value of 200 mm for the length of the specimen is used for this parametric analysis.

Bending stiffness matrix D is calculated for a typical stiffener laminates and dimensions. These values are divided by the inertia moment per unit length $t^3/12$ in order to take into account the effect of stiffener thickness. Figures 1 and 2 show the relation between inertia moment and local buckling strain values of T and I stiffener as a function of cap dimensions for different values of stiffener web thickness. The following conclusions can be obtained from these figures:

- inertia moment for I section decreases as cap dimension increases for a fixed value of area and laminate thickness. The effect is more patent as thickness increases or section area decrease.

- for all cases, crippling strains for T stiffener are lower than for I stiffener.

Bending stiffness of T section is greater than I section, and for buckling and fuel pressure T section should be selected. Only when crippling strain of T is not sufficient, I section should be selected.

OPTIMIZATION OF SPECIMEN DIMENSIONS FOR CRIPPLING TEST

Typical set-up for crippling test is shown in figure 3. There are two issues with this type of specimens. The first is the determination of the specimen length, because Euler buckling may be produced before crippling. On the other hand, if specimen length is too short, conditions at the end may affect the whole specimen behaviour.

The second issue is to select the specimen width to avoid local buckling between the edge support and the stiffener, see fig. 3, before the local buckling of one stiffener flange.

To select these dimensions, a finite element model for T stiffener is made, using 150 mm skin width and 140 mm length. MSC/NASTRAN finite element code is used. The first buckling mode is at skin, between teflon support and the end of stiffener flange(figure 4), when the stiffener flange is 50 mm. The model is modified to a skin width of 100 mm. being now the first buckling mode at stiffener web, as shown in figure 5.

Additional buckling analyses are made with different stiffener lengths. Variation of buckling strain with specimen length is provided in figure 6. In all cases, buckling occurs at stiffener web. This figure also includes buckling strain obtained from reference 1. Apparently, as stiffener length increases, buckling strain approaches to an asymptotic value, decreasing the effect of clamping conditions at end of specimen. However, if length is too large there may be Euler buckling. The limit is imposed by the condition:

$$L'/\rho < 15$$

where L' is the equivalent length and ρ is the radius of gyration.

TEST SPECIMEN, INSTRUMENTATION AND LOADS

The first set of specimens was selected according to analysis of previous sections. T and I section are used. The second one was select to verify the influence of parameter such as stiffener web thickness, flange length, web height and skin thickness. In all cases stiffener stacking is 60% 0° layers, 30% 45° and 10% 90°. For the skin a laminate of 30% 0°, 60% 45° and 10% 90° is selected. Table 1 shows the number of specimens of each type.

Clamped conditions at specimens end is obtained introducing the specimens in high modulus resin blocks. In some specimens artificial defects to simulate maximum production defects are included.

Local buckling and crippling strain are obtained from strain-gauge located as shown in figure 7.

Several specimens are loaded under fatigue. A sinusoidal fatigue spectrum between $-4000\mu\epsilon$ and $0\mu\epsilon$ is introduced up to 250000 cycles.

TEST RESULTS

Typical strain-gauge records are shown in figure 8. Strain measures at both sides of stiffener web show a local buckling at 25000dN. An increase in load is supported by stringer foot corners, followed by decrease in specimen stiffness. Crippling is obtained as a mean value of final strain values at the foot.

Table 2 shows average results for each type of specimen.

ANALYTICAL CORRELATION

Stiffener cross section is idealized in terms of interconnected flat laminates as shown in figure 9. From equation (2) and (3) local buckling strain is obtained for each laminate. These values are compared with test results, being the calculation conservative in a 10%.

Parameters α y β of equation (3) are obtained by interpolation. Values for α are between 0.618 and 0.795. Limits for β are 0.685 and 0.961. The variability is due to the scatter in test results. These results, compared with those of reference 1 show the strong dependence of α and β parameters on the material. Results and conclusions are in agreement with references [2] to [5].

Other conclusions obtained from test results are:

- fatigue loads introduce a reduction factor of 8% over static results.
- artificial defects introduce a reduction factor between 5% and 10%.
- larger radius at stiffener flange-web corner increases crippling strain.

INTERNAL FUEL PRESSURE LOAD

Internal fuel pressure produces an increase of interlaminar stresses at skin-stiffener interface, both shear and peel stresses. Failure mode is debonding of the two elements.

In order to develop a failure criterion based on interlaminar stresses at skin-stiffener interface a finite element method analysis is performed. The model includes an idealization of interface according to reference [7]. An internal fuel pressure load of 0.32 Mpa is considered.

For more accuracy a nonlinear analysis is performed. Figure 10 shows the deformed geometry at ultimate load. Stress distribution shows a good correlation with failure criterion proposed in reference 8, being the form:

$$\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{a11}}\right)^x + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{a11}}\right)^y = 1 \quad (4)$$

CONCLUSIONS

A simple design methodology for CFC stiffener has been presented, including selection of stiffener shape and determination of crippling strain allowables. The method includes structural and productions requirements. Compared with test results calculations are conservative in a 10% for local buckling. Influence of fatigue load, artificial defects and radius of corners have been obtained.

For fuel pressure load a failure criteria taking into account interlaminar stresses is derived. Stresses are obtained from a detailed nonlinear finite element model with an idealization of skin-stiffener interface.

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TABLE 1.- TEST SUMMARY

DESIGNATION	SECTION	TEST CONDITION	DEFECTS	LOAD	No.
BE-A1	T	RT/AR	NO	STATIC	1
BE-A2 & BE-A3	T	RT/AR	YES	FATIGUE	2
BE-A4	T	H/W	YES	STATIC	1
BE-A5	T	H/W	NO	STATIC	1
BE-A6	T	RT/AR	NO	FATIGUE	1
BE-B1 & BE-B3	I	RT/AR	YES	STATIC	2
BE-B2	I	RT/AR	NO	STATIC	1
A 31/28	T	RT/AR	NO	STATIC	5
A 31/24	T	RT/AR	NO	STATIC	5
A 17/28	T	RT/AR	NO	STATIC	5
A 17/24	T	RT/AR	NO	STATIC	5

TABLE 2.- TEST RESULTS.

DESIGNATION	ϵ_{pt}	ϵ_{cr}
BE-A1	-5400	-8104
BE-A3	-5000	-7293
BE-A6	-4800	-6618
BE-B1	-	-6709
BE-B2	-	-7333
B2-B3	-	-6444
A 31/28	-5775	-7339
A 31/24	-4500	-6468
A 17/28	-5150	-7522
A 17/24	-4350	-5715

FIGURE 1.- INERTIA MOMENT RATIO vs. CAP DIMENSION.

FIGURE 2.- BUCKLING STRAIN RATIO vs. CAP DIMENSION.

FIGURE 3.- TEST SET-UP.

FIGURE 4.- FIRST F.E. MODEL.

FIGURE 5.- MODIFIED F.E. MODEL.

FIGURE 6.- BUCKLING STRAIN vs. SPECIMEN LENGTH.

FIGURE 7.- STRAIN-GAUGE LOCATION.

FIGURE 8.- STRAIN MEASURES.

FIGURE 9.- STIFFENER IDEALIZATION.

FIGURE 10.- DEFORMED GEOMETRY. FUEL PRESSURE LOAD.